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To cite this article: LufyDitya Cahyanti *et al* 2023 *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci.* **1266** 012075

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Morphophysiology responses of taro on different soil water level

LutfyDitya Cahyanti^{1,3*}, Edi Santosa², Didy Sopandic², and Heni Purnamawati²

¹Department Agronomy and Horticulture, Faculty of Agriculture, Graduate School, Bogor Agricultural University (IPB University). Jl. Meranti, Kampus IPB Dramaga, Bogor, 16680, Indonesia

²Department Agronomy and Horticulture, Faculty of Agriculture, Bogor Agricultural University (IPB University). Jl. Meranti, Kampus IPB Dramaga, Bogor, 16680, Indonesia

³Study Program of Agrotechnology, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of Darussalam Gontor (UNIDA Gontor), Jl. Raya Siman KM. 6, Siman, Ponorogo 63471, East Java, Indonesia

Email: edi_santosa@apps.ipb.ac.id

Abstract. This study aims to determine the response of growth and yield of taro plant genotypes to the level of soil water availability. The experiment was carried out using a divided plot design with the main plot being the rate of water application, namely: 60% FC (Field capacity), 80% FC, 100% FC, 120% FC and 140% FC, while the subplots were taro genotypes consisting of two types of dasheen (Ketan and California genotype), two types of eddoe (Satoimo and Jepang Hijau) also Xanthosoma (Talas Kuning). Parameters of plant growth observations included plant height, number of leaves, leaf area, stem diameter and width of canopy, while parameters of harvest observations included tuber fresh weight and total fresh weight. Physiological observations include chlorophyll content and number of stomata. Plant height of all types of taro was more vigor at 120 and 140% FC of water. For dasheen type taro, California taro with 140% FC treatment produced tuber fresh weight 36% higher than California taro plants at 60% FC treatment, while for Eddoetypetar, Satoimo taro with 140% FC treatment produced tuber fresh weight 25% higher than in 60% FC treatment. This proves that 5 genotypes of taro adaptive on waterlogging stress rather than drought stress. Satoimo and Jepang Hijau (eddoe type) are more adaptive to drought and wet soil conditions than talas Ketan, California and Talas Kuning (dasheen type).

1. Introduction

Climate change is responsible for changing seasons and rainfall patterns in Indonesia, which have affected agricultural commodities production significantly [1]. This causes a prolonged dry season phenomenon that leading to drought stress on cultivated plants. Climate change also increasing potential of flooding at rainy season which lead to waterlogging stress [2],[3]. According to world estimates, average yield losses in agricultural crops up to 50% is mainly due to different abiotic stresses as a result of these changing climatic conditions [4]. Drought stress and waterlogging stress is a factor causing a decrease in the productivity of cultivated plants because it will inhibit photosynthesis, disrupt water use efficiency, and change the physiological, biochemical, morphological and molecular characteristics of plants [5].

Indonesia is a country with a fairly high diversity of taro. Taro that is widely cultivated is *Colocasia* sp. and *Xanthosoma* sp. Taro plants are generally planted in well-watered land [6]. In Indonesia, various taro genotypes are popular that grow well in an area such as home garden, farmer field, riverbank, and swampy area [1], but research results showed that taro production was higher in sufficient water conditions. Water treatment at different intervals, 1 and 3 days watering resulted in a 2-3 fold increase in tuber fresh weight for all types of taro, compared to taro plants with intervals of watering 7 and 15 days [7], another research reporting that taro plants that were fed 1500 mm per season given once a day, showed the highest results in all components of growth and yield of taro plants [8].

Taro has the potential to fulfill foreign export markets, especially to Japan, this is because in recent years the demand for eddoe type taro from Indonesia has been so high, as much as 100,000 tons of taro per month [9]. One of the obstacles faced by farmers in taro cultivation is low productivity due to the phenomenon of climate change which causes taro to be cultivated in sub-optimal conditions, so studies are needed to obtain adaptive genotypes or keep growing stable and produce high quality tubers under drought and waterlogging condition [7]. The study of plant adaptation to drought and waterlogging can be approached by selecting the right genotype and experimenting with different levels of watering [3],[5]. This study aims to determine the response of growth and yield of taro plant genotypes to the level of soil water availability.

2. Materials

2.1 Place and time

The experiment was carried out from June 2022-March 2023 in the Cikabayan Experimental Field greenhouse, Bogor Agricultural University, Located at 6°33'5.06"S and 106°43'3.78"E. The type of soil used is ultisol. The temperature during the day during the study varied 30-40°C (average 35.5°C).

2.2 Tools and materials

The materials used were Satoimo, Jepang Hijau, Ketan, California and Talas Kuning genotypes. The equipment used is an analytical balance, camera, caliper.

3. Methodology

a. Research design

The experiment was carried out using a split plot design. The main plot consisted of 5 levels of groundwater availability based on field capacity (FC), namely: 60% FC, 80% FC, 100% FC, 120% FC and 140% FC, while the subplots consisted of 5 taro genotypes consisting of two types of *Colocasia esculenta* var *esculenta* or dasheen type (Ketan and California), two types of *Colocasia esculenta* var *antiquorum* or eddoe type (Satoimo and Jepang Hijau) and *Xanthosoma undipes* (Talas Kuning). Each experiment was repeated 3 times, so that 75 experimental units were obtained.

b. Media of planting preparation

The planting medium is a mixture of soil and manure, with a ratio of 20 kg of soil and 5 kg of manure, so that the total weight of the media is 25 kg. The planting media mixture is put into a polybag 40 cm x 40 cm.

c. Taro cultivation

The tubers were first sown for 8 weeks and transplanted after they had two fully opened leaves. Planting is done by placing one seed at the bottom of the polybag planting hole.

d. Field capacity measurement

Field capacity measurements were carried out by dousing the planting media in polybags with water until it dripped and then allowed to stand until no water dripped. Then the planting medium was weighed for wet weight and dry weight. Wet weight was weighed after no water dripped from the polybag. The dry weight was weighed after the planting medium was baked at 105°C for 24 hours, until a constant weight was obtained. Water requirements based on field capacity are calculated using a formula [10]:

$$FC (\%) = \frac{Tb - Tk}{Tk} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Note:

FC = Field capacity

Tb = Fresh weight Tk = Drought weight

e. Soil water availability treatment

Plants that were climatized for 4 weeks after planting (WAP) were treated with water availability levels based on field capacity of 60%, 80%, 100%, 120% and 140% FC. Treatment was given since the plants were 4 WAP to 20 WAP.

f. Morphological observation

Morphological observations were made on three sample plants in each treatment at each replication. Observations were made on the variables of plant height, number of leaves, stem diameter and crown width. Observation of plant height was measured from the soil surface to the tip of the petiole. The number of leaves is calculated from the leaves that have opened perfectly. Pseudostem diameter was observed at the base of the petiole using a caliper.

g. SPAD Value

SPAD values were measured at 16 and 20 WAP

h. Stomata observation

Stomata collection was carried at 20 WAP in the morning at 09.00-10.00 when the plant leaves received sunlight so that the stomata had fully opened. The leaves of the sample plants on the top and bottom surfaces were cleaned with a tissue to remove dust/dirt, then smeared with nail polish, left for 10 minutes, then the dried smear was pasted with insulation and leveled. The insulation is peeled off and taken slowly, then affixed to the glass slide. Furthermore, it is labeled with a description of the type of taro plant genotype. The stomata was observed on the microscope and counting of opened stomata by Image raster software.

i. Harvest observation

Harvesting was done at 24 WAP. The harvest variables include tuber fresh weight per plant, tuber dry weight per plant, total fresh weight of plant, and total dry weight of plant. Tubers fresh weight per plant was measured by taking three plants per replicate. The tubers that have been separated from the roots, then cleaned of the soil are weighed with an analytical balance. Total plant wet weight was measured by taking three plants per replicate. The plants are then cleaned from the soil and weighed with an analytical balance. Tuber dry weight and total dry weight of the plant was evaluated after oven drying at 80°C until constant weight.

j. *Data analysis*

The effect of treatment was analyzed by F test, while the difference in genotype average values was analyzed by 5% BNT analysis.

4. Result and Discussion

Taro plant height was significantly affected by the level of water availability and genotype (Table 1). Plant height at 120% water availability was not significantly different from plants at 140% FC water availability, but significantly different from plant height at 60, 80 and 100% FC. Plant height with a water availability level treatment 120% FC (159.33 cm) was significantly higher by 13% compared to plants treated with a water availability level of 80% FC (138.58 cm). Growth is accomplished through cell division, cell enlargement and differentiation, and involves genetic, physiological, ecological and morphological events and their complex.

Table 1. Morphology of taro plants 20 WAP on different levels of water availability

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Pseudostem Diameter (cm)	Number of leaf	Width of canopy (cm)
Water level treatment				
60% FC	140,69 c	19,76	4,31	77,51
80% FC	138,58 c	19,35	4,58	78,46
100% FC	145,38 b	19,91	4,44	77,12
120 % FC	159,33 a	20,55	4,51	80,46
140% FC	157,04 a	21,36	4,42	80,41
BNT 5%	4,52	ns	Ns	ns
Genotype				
Satoimo	138,56 d	19,44 b	4,48	78,07
Jepang Hijau	139,44 d	19,56 b	4,48	80,06
Ketan	163,11 b	22,07 a	4,33	78,07
California	170,96 a	22,70 a	4,52	80,26
Talas Kuning	149,70 c	19,26 b	4,48	80,19
BNT 5%	4,52	1,31	Ns	ns

The numbers in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different based on the LSD test at the 5% level.

Plant height of California genotype (170,96 cm) was higher compared to Ketan, Talas Kuning, Jepang Hijau, and Satoimo (Table 1), while Satoimo (138,56 cm) and Jepang Hijau (139,44 cm) has the lowest plant height compared to other genotypes. It is known that there are differences in the height of taro plants due to genetic influences [11]. Previous research found highly significant variation among taro varieties in terms of plant height [12][13]. A similar variation in plant height among taro genotypes was also reported on another research [14]. Taro grouped based on plant height into dwarf (<50 cm), medium (50-100 cm), and tall (>100) [15].

Taro pseudostem diameter was not affected by the level of water availability but significantly affected by genotype (Table 1). Ketan and California genotype producing largest pseudotem diameter than another genotypes. While number of leaf and width of canopy were not affected by water level treatment and genotypes.

Table 2. Leaf area of taro (cm²) at different levels of water availability

Treatment	Leaf Area (cm ²) 20 MST					Average
	Satoimo	Jepang Hijau	Ketan	California	Talas Kuning	
60% FC	938,00 d	975,67 d	1089,67 d	907,33 d	1055,00 e	993,134
80% FC	1032,67 c	1098,67 c	1158,67 c	1028,67 c	1135,33 d	1090,802
100% FC	1172,67 b	1190,33 b	1237,33 b	1150,00 b	1177,33 c	1185,532
120 % FC	1224,67 a	1280,33 a	1278,00 a	1266,33 a	1257,00 b	1261,266
140% FC	1266,00 a	1263,00 a	1234,33 b	1246,00 a	1351,67 a	1272,2
Average	1126,802	1161,6	1199,6	1119,666	1195,266	
BNT 5%	24,41					

The numbers in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different based on the LSD test at the 5% level

The interaction between plant genotype treatment and the level of water availability significantly affected the leaf of taro (Table 2). In saturated water level of 140% FC, Talas kuning had the widest leaf area (1352,67 cm²) while Ketan type had the narrowest leaf area (1234,33 cm²).

Response of plant to water stress begins with physiological process disturbance in the plant, such as reducing transpiration rate by means of stomata closure and reducing leaf surface area or leaf rolling.

Table 3. Tuber fresh weight of taro (g) at different levels of water availability

Treatment	Tuber fesh weight (g)					Average
	Satoimo	Jepang Hijau	Ketan	California	Talas Kuning	
60% FC	407,33 d	476,00 c	302,00 d	298,00 d	238,33 d	344,33
80% FC	414,33 d	506,00 b	335,33 c	301,00 d	330,33 c	377,39
100% FC	431,67 c	535,67 a	359,67 b	375,33 c	398,33 b	420,13
120 % FC	527,67 b	491,00 c	383,33 a	428,33 b	409,67 b	448,00
140% FC	549,00 a	535,67 a	393,33 a	463,33 a	481,00 a	484,46
Average	466,00	508,86	354,73	373,19	371,53	
BNT 5%	19,72					

The numbers in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different based on the LSD test at the 5% level.

The interaction between water availability and genotype significantly affected the fresh weight of taro tubers (Table 3). All taro genotypes treated with a water availability level of 140% FC produced tuber fresh weights heavier than plants treated with water availability of 60, 80, 100 and 120% FC. The Satoimo genotype produced the heaviest tuber fresh weight compared to the other genotypes. Treatment with a water availability level of 140% for the Satoimo genotype resulted in a fresh tuber weight of 549 g or 26% heavier than the Satoimo genotype with a water availability level treatment of 60% FC which resulted in a fresh tuber weight of 407.33 g. The optimal formation of assimilate is supported by the adequacy of water as a raw material for photosynthesis [16], so that more and more assimilate is produced and will increase the weight of plant tubers [8].

Table 4. Total fresh weight of plant (gram) at different levels of water availability

Treatment	Total fresh weight of plant (gram)					Average
	Satoimo	Jepang Hijau	Ketan	California	Talas Kuning	
60% FC	1024,33 d	1067,00 d	963,22 d	1169,11 c	1140,78 e	1072,88
80% FC	1057,67 c	1122,44 c	956,33 d	1156,56 c	1237,00 d	1106,00
100% FC	1071,11 c	1192,22 b	1062,56 c	1238,44 b	1443,11 c	1201,48
120 % FC	1216,78 b	1176,56 b	1278,78 b	1501,44 a	1611,33 b	1356,97
140% FC	1374,89 a	1449,67 a	1379,00 a	1517,22 a	1659,33 a	1476,02
Average	1148,95	1201,57	1127,97	1316,55	1418,31	
BNT 5%	32,92					

The numbers in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different based on the LSD test at the 5% level.

The interaction between plant genotype treatment and the level of water availability significantly affected the total fresh weight of taro (Table 4). All taro genotypes treated with a water availability level of 140% FC resulted in a higher total plant fresh weight compared to plants treated with water availability of 60, 80, 100 and 120% FC. Talas Kuning genotype produced the highest total plant fresh weight compared to the other genotypes. Treatment with a water availability level of 140% for Talas

Kuning genotype resulted in a total plant fresh weight of 1659.33 g or 31% heavier than Talas Kuning genotype with a water availability level treatment of 60% KL (1140.78 g).

There was no interaction between plant genotype treatment and the level of water availability on tuber dry weight of taro (Table 5). Tuber dry weight at 140% FC treatment was not significantly different from plants at 120% FC water treatment, but significantly different from tuber dry weight at 60, 80 and 100% FC. 140% FC water treatment resulting tuber dry weight 16% heavier than tuber dry weight at 60% FC treatment. Decrease in soil moisture drastically caused by decreasing water level treatment reduced leaf area, leaf longevity, stomatal opening and dry matter production also corm yield in taro [17].

Table 5. Tuber dry weight of taro (g) at different levels of water availability

Treatment	Tuber dry weight (g)
Water level treatment	
60% FC	33,07 b
80% FC	35,53 b
100% FC	35,53 b
120 % FC	37,33 a
140% FC	38,53 a
BNT 5%	3,14
Genotipe	
Satoimo	38,89 a
Jepang Hijau	39,11 a
Ketan	32,77 b
California	32,89 b
Talas Kuning	39,11 a
BNT 5%	3,14

The numbers in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different based on the LSD test at the 5% level.

Table 6. Total dry weight of plant (g) at different levels of water availability

Treatment	Total dry weight of plant (g)					Average
	Satoimo	Jepang Hijau	Ketan	California	Talas Kuning	
60% FC	86,47 d	76,27 e	91,70 d	88,87 e	98,67 e	88,396
80% FC	88,10 d	82,57 d	92,50 d	93,73 d	103,60 d	92,1
100% FC	92,47 c	97,60 c	102,07 c	105,07 c	122,77 b	103,996
120 % FC	110,50 b	109,90 b	115,30 b	120,33 b	115,90 c	114,386
140% FC	116,73 a	125,93 a	128,47 a	128,73 a	134,00 a	126,772
Average	98,854	98,454	106,008	107,346	114,988	
BNT 5%			2,88			

The numbers in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different based on the LSD test at the 5% level

The interaction between plant genotype treatment and the level of water availability significantly affected the total dry weight of taro (Table 6). All taro genotypes treated with a water availability level of 140% FC resulted in a higher total dry weight compared to plants treated with water availability of

60, 80, 100 and 120% FC. Final total dry weight of plant was shown to decrease in response to decreasing water availability. This concurs with another research reported that drought responses that favoured avoidance and escape were often to the detriment of yield due to reduced crop duration and biomass production [18], and many yield-determining plant processes are affected by water stress [19].

There was no interaction between plant genotype treatment and the level of water availability on SPAD Value at 16 and 20 WAP (Table 7). SPAD value was related with chlorophyll content of plants. There was significant effect of water level treatment at total chlorophyll content. 100% FC water level treatment resulting the highest chlorophyll content at 16 and 20 WAP, and significantly different from taro with another water treatment. At 16 WAP, chlorophyll content from genotype with 100% FC water level treatment is 17% and 21% higher than chlorophyll content from genotype with 140% and 60% FC water level treatment. The water synthesis of chlorophyll is very important, after a heavy rain the amount of chlorophyll increases, but in the arid time its value decreases. On the other hand, if the soil is water saturated, leaves chlorophyll content decreases. The amount of leaf water needed to maintain the maximum amount of chlorophyll should be high [20].

Table 7. SPAD Value at different levels of water availability

Treatment	SPAD Value	
	16 WAP	20 WAP
Water level treatment		
60% FC	48,13 c	48,59 b
80% FC	48,61 c	45,50 b
100% FC	58,51 a	56,43 a
120 % FC	55,17 b	59,57 a
140% FC	51,39 c	48,66 b
BNT 5%	3,63	4,85
Genotype		
Satoimo	52,33	53,39
Jepang Hijau	54,73	55,44
Ketan	51,24	52,80
California	50,74	50,36
Talas Kuning	55,28	52,09
BNT 5%	ns	ns

The numbers in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different based on the LSD test at the 5% level

The interaction between plant genotype treatment and the level of water availability significantly affected the number stomata of taro (Table 8). All taro genotypes treated with a water availability level of 100% FC resulted in a higher number of stomata compared to genotype treated with water availability of 60, 80, 120 and 140% FC. Ketan genotype with 100% FC water level has the highest number of stomata, 41% higher than Ketan genotype with 60% FC water level treatment. Observation of stomata density at black rice show that, the lowest water treatment resulting the lowest density of stomata as morphological response [21].

Table 8. Number stomata at different levels of water availability

Treatment	Number of stomata					Average
	Satoimo	Jepang Hijau	Ketan	California	Talas Kuning	
60% FC	17,00 d	13,33 b	25,33 c	17,33 c	21,67 c	18,932
80% FC	15,67 d	15,67 b	28,67 b	26,00 b	24,33 c	22,068
100% FC	33,67 a	22,67 a	43,33 a	31,67 a	41,33 a	34,534
120 % FC	21,67 c	14,00 b	24,00 c	30,00 b	24,00 c	22,734
140% FC	28,33 b	20,67 a	33,00 b	29,33 b	28,33 b	27,932
Mean	23,268	17,268	30,866	26,866	27,932	
Average			4,49			

The numbers in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different based on the LSD test at the 5% level

5. Conclusion

Plant height of all types of tarowas more vigor at 120 and 140% FC of water. For dasheen type taro, California taro with 140% FC treatment produced tuber fresh weight 36% higher than California taro plants at 60% FC treatment, while for Eddoetype taro, Satoimo taro with 140% FC treatment produced tuber fresh weight 25% higher than in 60% FC treatment. Satoimo and Jepang Hijau (eddoe type) are more adaptive to drought and wet soil conditions than talas Ketan, California and Talas Kuning (dasheen type).

Acknowledgment

The authors acknowledge to the Ministry of Education, Culture and Higher Education, Republic of Indonesia for the financial support of this research, under scheme of “Grant for Dissertation Research” granted to Prof. Dr. Edi Santosa, M.Si. Grant number: 3776/IT3.LI/PT.01.03/P/B/2022 for FY 2022, and 001/E5/PG.02.00/2023 for FY 2023.

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